

Apolipoprotein B along with AIP as useful predictor of CVD among primary hypertensives

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Hypertension is defined as an average systolic blood pressure (SBP) \geq 140 mmHg, an average diastolic blood pressure (DBP) \geq 90 mmHg on three successive blood pressure measurements. It is classified as either primary/essential hypertension or secondary hypertension. Primary/Essential hypertension is the form of hypertension that by definition has no underlying cause. **Materials and Methods:** This study is a case control study conducted in the G R Medical College associated J A Group of hospitals Gwalior MP. In this study 100 Essential hypertensives and 100 normal healthy controls were taken. Lipid profile and Apolipoproteins were analysed. Total cholesterol, Triglyceride, HDL-C were analysed by enzymatic method while LDL-C and VLDL-C were calculated by Friedewald's calculation. Apolipoprotein A1 and Apolipoprotein B were analysed by Immunoturbidimetry method. All the biochemical variables were analysed by the help of B A 400 fully automated analyser. AIP was calculated as TG/HDL-C. **Results:** In the present study Total Cholesterol, LDL-C, VLDL-C were found extremely statistically significant with p value <0.0001 while Triglyceride, HDL-C were slightly significant. Apolipoprotein A1 was found slightly decreased level in essential hypertensive group as compare to controls. Apolipoprotein B was found extremely statistically significant with p value <0.0001 . AIP (TG/HDL-C) level was also found extremely statistically significant with p value <0.0001 . **Conclusion:** The study concluded Apolipoprotein B along with Atherogenic Indices of Plasma (TG/HDL-C) can be the emerging parameter to diagnose the CVDs in essential hypertensives.

Keywords: Hypertension, Apolipoproteins, CVD

INTRODUCTION:

According to the seventh report of the Joint National Committee on Prevention, Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Pressure (JNC 7), Hypertension was defined as an average systolic blood pressure (SBP) \geq 140 mmHg, an average diastolic blood pressure (DBP) \geq 90 mmHg on three successive blood pressure measurements, and/or current treatment for hypertension with anti-hypertensive medication. Stage-2 hypertension was defined as an average SBP \geq 160 mmHg and/or DBP \geq 100 mmHg. (Chobanian A. V. et al 2003).

The current definition of hypertension (HTN) is systolic blood pressure (SBP) values of 130 mm Hg or more and/or diastolic blood pressure (DBP) of more than 80 mm Hg. Hypertension ranks among the most common chronic medical condition characterized by a persistent elevation in arterial pressure. Hypertension has been among the most studied topics of the previous century and has been one of the most significant comorbidities contributing to the development of stroke,

myocardial infarction, heart failure, and renal failure. The definition and categories of hypertension have been evolving over the years, but there is a consensus that persistent BP readings of 140/90 mm Hg or more should undergo treatment with the usual therapeutic target of 130/80 mm Hg or less. (Frost CD et al 1991, Guyton AC et al 1972).

Hypertension is classified as either primary/essential hypertension or secondary hypertension. Primary/Essential hypertension is the form of hypertension that by definition has no underlying cause (Carretero et al 2000). It is the most common cause of hypertension affecting 90-95% of total hypertensive patients. The prevalence of hypertension has increased to the point where it is now a serious public health issue worldwide. It is the leading cause of chronic illness treated in primary care clinics and the most common type of non-communicable disease (Kossaify et al 2014). In 1975, there were 590 million people (14.5%) with high blood pressure around the

world. This number went up to 1.13 billion (15.3%) in 2015.

Essential hypertension remains a major modifiable risk factor for cardiovascular diseases despite important advances in our understanding of its patho-physiology and availability of effective treatment strategies. High blood pressure increases the risk of CVD for millions of people worldwide. Several prospective studies have identified the major risk factors for hypertension like obesity, smoking, and alcohol consumption, dyslipidemia apart from dietary patterns (Bhavani et al 2003).

Essential hypertension, a major health problem in the developed countries, affecting nearly one billion people worldwide (Kotchen T A et al) Accounting for about 57% of all deaths due to stroke and 24% of all deaths due to coronary heart disease in India(Gupta R et al 2013). It has a strong association with cardiovascular disease and contributes greatly to morbidity, mortality and economic burden (Buttar HS et al 2005) By 2025, the number of hypertensive individuals may rise to 213 million from 118 million in 2000 (Reddy KS et al 2005).

Apolipoprotein B (Apo B) is the major protein constituent of low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C). Increased serum level of LDL-C is recognized to be an independent risk factor for atherosclerotic-related events (Michos ED et al 2019). According to the amount of cholesterol ester in the core of LDL-C particle, LDL-C particles are different in sizes and densities such as small, intermediate and large dense LDLs, containing one molecule of Apo B per LDL-C particle regardless of its size. Although in most cases, the independent risk factor for atherosclerotic-related events is not smaller LDL particles, subjects with more of this type of LDL particles will be at higher risk for future cardiovascular events. However, epidemiological studies still fail to distinguish the relative atherogenicity caused by different sizes of LDL particles. This suggests that it is not the composition (sizes and densities) of LDL-C particles, but its quantity (Apo B content) that is the key factor of atherosclerosis. Smaller LDL particles are more likely to enter the arterial wall, and are more susceptible to oxidation, which is essentially as a result of the conformation-changing of Apo B with decreasing LDL particles size. For most individuals, the serum level of Apo B is largely concordant with that of LDL-C, and adds minor effect to LDL-C based risk assessment. However, in a subgroup with inconsistency between the serum levels of Apo B and LDL-C, there is a redundant risk is related to an excess

risk of atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD). (Sniderman AD et al 2019).

Apolipoprotein A1 (ApoA1) is the chief structural protein of anti- atherogenic HDL-C. It plays an essential role in reverse cholesterol transport and cellular cholesterol balance by activating Lacithin cholesterol esterase enzyme (Frank PG et al 2000). Lipoproteins and Apolipoproteins play crucial roles in health and a variety of diseases, particularly in the cardiovascular disease field (Zijun MA et al 2024).

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

In our study we have taken 100 hundred newly diagnosed adult essential hypertensive patients and an equal number of age- and sex matched controls without hypertension were consecutively recruited. The study was conducted in Gajara Raja Medical College and associated J A Group of Hospitals Gwalior MP. It was a hospital-based cross-sectional study. Relevant socio demographic data and history were obtained, physical examination was carried out, and anthropometric measurements were taken during subjects' first visits to the hospital. Blood pressure was taken on the left arm after 5 minutes' relaxation, in a sitting position, using a standard mercury sphygmomanometer with appropriate cuff size, systolic (SBP) and diastolic (DBP) blood pressures corresponded to Korotkoff sounds 1 and V, respectively. We have taken average of three readings, at first visit, was used for further analysis. Height and body weight were measured with participants standing without shoes and heavy outer garments. Body mass index (BMI) was calculated as weight, divided by height squared (kg/m²). Fasting serum lipid profile were determined using a 5 mL sample of blood obtained from an antecubital vein following an overnight (i.e., about 9–12-hour) fast. Serum total cholesterol (TC), high density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C), and triglycerides (TG) were determined enzymatically, while low density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) and very low density lipoprotein (VLDL-C) was calculated using the Friedwald's formula. Apo lipoprotein A1 and Apo B were determined by the help of BA 400 fully automated biosystem biochemistry analyser establishing in the lab using immune turbidimetry method.

We have selected pure essential hypertensive subjects for this study. Subjects with Secondary hypertension, liver diseases, kidney diseases, Cardiovascular diseases, thyroid diseases, malignancy, past cardiovascular incidences, diabetes mellitus were excluded from the study. Women with pregnancy were also excluded by questionnaire.

RESULTS:

Table-1 Comparison of Anthropometric Parameters in case and control group

Parameters	Case (N=100) (Mean±SD)	Control(N=100) (Mean±SD)	P value
Age	42.71±10.92	40.92±9.31	0.013
Weight	66.76±8.42	63.15±9.00	0.003
BMI	29.61±2.30	22.82±1.73	<0.0001
SBP	150.37±14.51	123.93±4.88	<0.0001
DBP	111.30±16.38	83.28±4.30	<0.0001

Note- BMI= Body mass index, SBP= Systolic blood pressure, DBP- Diastolic blood pressure.

Figure 1: Comparison of Anthropometric Parameters in case and control group**Table-2 Comparison of Lipid profile and their fractions in case and control group**

Parameters	Case (N=100) (Mean±SD)	Control (N=100) (Mean±SD)	P Value
TC (mg/dl)	202.05±41.49	182.49±13.60	<0.0001
TG (mg/dl)	120.24±30.95	108.34±19.93	0.001
HDL -C (mg/dl)	50.24±8.91	54.59±13.25	0.007
LDL-C (mg/dl)	127.75±41.22	108.73±16.44	<0.0001
VLDL-C (mg/dl)	25.05±7.12	17.07±2.12	<0.0001
TG/HDL-C	2.70±1.19	1.60± 0.76	<0.0001

Note- TC= Total Cholesterol, TG-Triglycerides, HDL-C= High density lipoprotein, LDL-C= Low density lipoproteins, VLDL-C= Very low density lipoproteins, TG/HDL= AIP (Atherogenic indices of plasma)

Figure 2- Comparison of lipid profile between case and control group

Table-3 Apolipoprotein A1 and Apolipoprotein B level in case and control group

Parameter	Case (N=100) (Mean±SD)	Control (N=100) (Mean±SD)	P value
Apo A1	145.10±12.10	149.12±13.08	0.02
Apo B	115.96±14.67	87.52±11.41	<0.0001

Note- Apo A1= Apolipoprotein A1, Apo B= Apolipoprotein B

Figure 3 Comparison of Apo A1 and Apo B between Cases and Controls

Figure 4 Comparison of TG/HDL-C Ratio between Cases and Controls

Table 1 Shows the comparison of anthropometric parameters between essential hypertensive case group and normal healthy normotensive control group. Present data shows systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure and body mass index were extremely statistically significant increased in essential hypertensive group as compare to normal healthy control group.

Table 2 Shows lipid parameters as Total cholesterol, LDL-C, VLDL-C were statistically significantly increased in essential hypertensive group as compare to normotensive control group. Triglycerides and HDL-C were significant in essential hypertensive group as compare to the control group.

Table 3 Shows Apolipoprotein B was found extremely highly significant as compare to control group while Apolipoprotein A1 was found not significant i in essential hypertensives group as compare to control group.

Figure 3 Shows Atherogenic Index of plasma (AIP) was found extremely stastically high in essential hypertensive group as compare to control group.

DISCUSSION:

In our study the main effort was to establish relationship among Apolipoproteins and Atherogenic Indices of Plasma (AIP). We found significant elevated level of Apolipoprotein B in the essential hypertensive subjects compare to control subjects. Similarly Israa Nathir et al 2023 has found in their study and reported the risk of developing CAD is significantly increased in patient with hypertension followed by higher Apolipoprotein B. Apo B may be linked by a variety of pathways to the development of CAD in hypertensive patients. These pathways include the infiltration and retention of lipoprotein containing Apolipoprotein B in the arterial wall, the stimulation of

endothelial dysfunction and an increase in the severity of coronary artery stenosis (Dexler et al 1997). Apolipoprotein B (protein transporting molecules) is present in all types of atherogenic lipoproteins including LDL-C, VLDL-C and IDL-C and their determination enables a more accurate estimation of atherogenicity than the traditional lipid biomarker (Sniderman A D et al 1997). Apolipoprotein B is involved in atherogenesis is complex. Apo B capture in the arterial wall is the main initiating factor in atherogenesis. This leads to the accumulation of lipids, triggering a cellular response in the arterial wall which results in the acceleration of the lipid accumulation process by secretory sphingomylinase, lipoprotein lipase and phospholipase A2 (Malikmohammad et al 2021). Similar to our study Maria Dorobant et al 2023 has found elevated level of Apolipopriten B in their study and they have reported in their study that Apolipoprotein B may be considered as a risk factor for CVD, promoting atherosclerosis and associated with increased expression of classical markers of clinical or subclinical CVD. Their finding suggests that elevated Apolipoprotein B is a risk factor for CVDs and is involved in different stages of atherosclerosis progression. Moreover in accordance with our study Alma Nurtazania et al 2020, Rehab Ibrahim Yaseen et al 2021, Dubey R et al 2023, Bandana et al 2024 etc. recent studies also has found significant elevated level of Apolipoprotein B in hypertensive group as compare to normal subjects which suggests Apolipoprotein B should be used in regular analytical blood measures to prevent cardiovalcular diseases in essential hypertension.

In this study we have found significantly high level of AIP (TG/HDL-C) in essential hypertensive group as compare to normal group. Many previous studies have also found elevated level of AIP in

hypertensive group patients as compare to the normotensive group which are supporting our study. Yen-Wei Li et al 2021, Juan Yin et al 2021, Huancong Zheng et al 2024, Shabnam Niroumand et al 2015, Rajaraghupathy Sujatha et al (2017) ,Tomas Sastre alzamora et al (2024), Osman Turak et al (2016), Nagababu Pyadala et al (2016). AIP can be easily estimated from routinely done parameters and is therefore cheaper alternative to other costly diagnostic tests.

CONCLUSION:

Apolipoprotein B along with AIP has emerged as an important parameters for the evaluation of risk of future cardiovascular diseases in essential/Primary hypertensive patients. Based on the present study, and according to the epidemiological transition of disease, life style change, performing regular exercise and healthy diet modification is recommended to prevent CVDs in future.

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